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Children's enjoyment of play during school lunchtime breaks:

An examination of intra- and inter-day reliability

Original Research

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Enjoyment and play during school lunchtime are correlated with children's physical
3 activity. Despite this, there is an absence of studies reporting children's enjoyment of play during
4 school lunchtime breaks. The purpose of this study was to examine the intra-day and inter-day
5 reliability of children's enjoyment of school lunchtime play. **Methods:** Surveys used to assess
6 children's enjoyment of lunchtime play were distributed to and completed by 197 children (112
7 males, 85 females), aged 8-12 years attending an elementary school in Victoria, Australia. Children
8 completed the surveys during class before lunch (expected enjoyment) and after lunch (actual
9 enjoyment) for five days. The intra- and inter-day enjoyment of school lunchtime play reliability
10 were determined using a weighted kappa. **Results:** Intra-day kappa values ranged from fair (0.31) to
11 substantial (0.75) within each of the five days (median kappa=0.41). In comparison, 'expected' (0.09-
12 0.40; median 0.30) and 'actual' (0.05-0.46; median 0.28) inter-day enjoyment of lunchtime play
13 displayed low reliability. **Conclusions:** Children's enjoyment of lunchtime play appears to be more
14 consistent within days than across days. The findings suggest that assessment of children's enjoyment
15 of lunchtime play once on a single day would be representative of a particular day but not necessarily
16 that particular school week.

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1 **Background**

2 The development of healthy lifestyle behaviours early in life is important. Childhood is a crucial time
3 to develop activity habits that can prevent potential health consequences associated with a sedentary
4 lifestyle in adulthood.¹ Schools have been identified as a major setting for children to participate in
5 physical activity and are being targeted to increase fitness standards among young people to reduce
6 the prevalence of childhood obesity.² A range of physical activity opportunities are present in schools
7 including physical education, sport programs, after school activities and play during school breaks.³
8 However, there are a number of barriers to implementing physical education effectively and in most
9 countries physical education doesn't provide sufficient physical activity for children to meet national
10 physical activity guidelines.⁴⁻⁶ With school curricular time devoted to children and adolescents'
11 physical education declining,^{7, 8} and to reduce the burden on schools to provide physical education,
12 sport and after school activity programs, there is an increasing trend towards schools facilitating
13 children's physical activity via non-curricular avenues such as play during school breaks.^{3, 9-12} Play
14 during school breaks is now recognised as the major source for children's daily physical activity,^{3, 12-}
15 ¹⁴ contributing up to 50% of children's recommended daily physical activity. Evidence suggests
16 children spend up to 35% of school breaks engaged in moderate to vigorous physical activity
17 (MVPA).⁸ With children reported to be spending approximately 30 hours per week at school,⁸ access
18 and opportunities for physical activity during periods other than school breaks are limited, therefore
19 developing a greater understanding of children's play during school lunchtime is vital.

20

21 An essential element of tailoring physical activity interventions to target children's requires
22 identification of key psychosocial correlates that may explain behaviour change.¹⁵ Children's physical
23 activity behaviour can include active play,¹⁶ structured sport,¹⁷ physical education¹⁸ and active
24 transport.¹⁹ Many studies have been conducted to identify the psychosocial correlates of childhood
25 physical activity.^{15, 20} A comprehensive review of 108 studies published over 28 years was conducted
26 by Sallis and colleagues.¹⁵ The psychosocial correlates that were consistently linked to childhood
27 physical activity behavior included exercise motivation, social support and self efficacy. A review of
28 studies (n=60) published between 1999 and 2005 identified the same key psychosocial correlates of

1 physical activity²⁰ and suggested that further investigation into the psychosocial correlates of children
2 and adolescent physical activity is still warranted.^{15, 20, 21}
3
4 More recently, research has examined the association between the psychosocial correlate 'enjoyment'
5 and children's physical activity. The connection between enjoyment and behavior change can be
6 explained by the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) which outlines that if behavior such as physical
7 activity is motivated by intrinsic factors (e.g. experiencing enjoyment after exercise) physical activity
8 participation is more likely to be sustained than via extrinsic factors (e.g. obtaining rewards).²²
9 Enjoyment has been shown to be positively correlated with children's motivation for involvement,²³
10 and sustained participation in sport²³ and physical activity.^{24, 25} There are numerous developmental
11 physical and psychological benefits associated with an active lifestyle, however a 'lack of enjoyment'
12 has been identified as a potential determinant of declining participation in physical activity.²⁶ Similar
13 to the Self-Determination Theory, The Youth Physical Activity Promotion (YPAP) model proposed
14 by Welk suggests that if children enjoy participating in particular activities, they are more likely to
15 engage in and maintain participation in those activities.²⁷ This model is supported by Moore and
16 colleagues' suggestion that personal benefits associated with physical activity, especially enjoyment,
17 are correlated with participation in physical activity.²⁴ Enjoyment is derived intrinsically via
18 kinaesthetic experiences and achievement of personal goals and extrinsically via social recognition
19 and comparative achievement.²⁸ Researchers define enjoyment of physical activity as "a positive
20 affective response to an experience that reflects generalized feelings such as pleasure, liking, and fun
21 (p.32)."²⁸ Therefore, with so many experiences encountered by children from day to day, psychosocial
22 influences on behaviour such as enjoyment are an important consideration when assessing the
23 physical activity and health behaviour of children and adolescents.
24
25 A number of studies have recognised the positive association between children's enjoyment of
26 physical activity and participation. Di Lorenzo and colleagues²⁹ examined the affects of a number of
27 psychological and environmental variables on physical activity participation and reported that
28 enjoyment was the main predictor of physical activity participation amongst children in grades five

1 and six. In addition, a study conducted over a decade ago revealed that enjoyment of physical
2 education among school children was strongly correlated with increased physical activity levels³⁰ and
3 this correlation was recently reinforced in a study examining the association of structured physical
4 activities with enjoyment of physical education.³¹ Other studies have also identified associations
5 between enjoyment and correlates of physical activity including self-determination,³² motor skill
6 proficiency,³³ task orientation,³⁴ self-efficacy,³⁵ goal setting,³⁵ and perceived competence.³⁴

7
8 School-based physical activity interventions have targeted enjoyment as a key psychosocial mediator
9 of behavioural changes.^{25, 36} An intervention known as 'Switch Play' aimed to prevent unhealthy
10 weight gain by reducing sedentary time in 10 year old children.²⁵ Children reported high enjoyment
11 levels and increased physical activity levels after the intervention.²⁵ Measurement of children's
12 enjoyment is used not only as part of cross-sectional research when assessing correlates of physical
13 activity but also when evaluating the effectiveness of physical activity interventions. However, many
14 studies investigating enjoyment did not consider the extent to which measuring enjoyment may vary
15 within and between school days.

16
17 No study we are aware of has assessed children's enjoyment of lunchtime play, however instruments
18 have been developed to identify children's enjoyment of physical activity. Motl and colleagues refined
19 the physical activity enjoyment scale (PACES) originally designed for college students to be suitable
20 for adolescents by replacing a seven point scale with a five point scale.³⁷ Within two studies targeting
21 adolescent females, positive correlations between enjoyment of physical activity and self-reported
22 physical activity, sports participation³⁷ and physical activity increases via a school-based lifestyle
23 intervention were reported.³⁸ The PACES terminology was recently simplified and validated for
24 younger children by Moore and colleagues.²⁴ Data from the PACES validation study revealed strong
25 correlations between children's enjoyment of physical activity with children's self-reported
26 perceptions of task goal orientation, physical appearance, athletic competence and physical activity.²⁴
27 In contrast to the PACES instrument that measures enjoyment of being physically active in general,
28 the present study assessed children's enjoyment of lunchtime play during lunchtime breaks within the

1 school setting. Positive correlations exist between children's enjoyment of physical activity and
2 participation,^{24, 25} yet little is known about children's enjoyment of play during school lunchtime
3 breaks, a major source of children's physical activity, both on a single day and across days of the
4 week.³⁹

5
6 Play during school lunchtime breaks is crucial for children's development of cognitive, physical,
7 social and emotional well-being^{16, 40} and play has been acknowledged by the United Nations High
8 Commission for Human Rights as an entitlement for every child.⁴¹ School lunchtime breaks provide
9 children with an avenue to engage in unstructured active play that includes self-directed activities to
10 build active, healthy bodies.¹⁶ When play is driven by children rather than adults, it allows children to
11 pursue activities within the environment that interests them, which can develop decision making,
12 negotiating and motor skills.¹⁶ Ultimately, the more positive responses (e.g. enjoyment) children
13 experience via active play through avenues such as unstructured school lunchtime breaks the more
14 likely children will adopt an active lifestyle and minimize the adoption of passive sedentary
15 behaviours such as using electronic media for entertainment.¹⁶ More research relating to predisposing
16 factors of physical activity such as enjoyment²⁷ and their associations with play during school
17 lunchtime are needed.¹² Measuring children's self-reported enjoyment of school lunchtime
18 experiences may reflect the quality of the school play environment. A greater understanding of
19 children's enjoyment of play within the school context is an important consideration in future
20 evaluations of interventions designed to improve or change play environments.^{37, 38} Determining the
21 consistency of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play within and between school days may also
22 provide evidence for health professionals and researchers of the frequency of measurement necessary
23 to provide a representative assessment of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play.

24
25 Recent studies have explored the intra⁴²⁻⁴⁴ and inter-day patterns⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ of children's physical activity
26 across multiple school days. However, none of these studies considered children's enjoyment levels.
27 To our knowledge, no study has previously reported children's enjoyment levels of school lunchtime
28 play or age/sex-specific enjoyment of lunchtime play variability. The question of whether children's

1 enjoyment of lunchtime play is representative of other school days is currently unknown. The
2 purposes of the present study were to (i) examine children's enjoyment of play during school lunch
3 time⁴⁸ examine the intra- and inter-day reliability of children's enjoyment of playing at lunchtime and
4 (iii) examine the age and sex-specific intra- and inter-day variability of children's enjoyment of
5 lunchtime play.

6

7 **Methods**

8 During the pilot study, survey cards were administered to 107 grade 3-6 children (aged 8-12 years) in
9 two elementary schools from regional Victoria. Children reported little concern or difficulty when
10 using the small survey cards, therefore no changes were necessary for the current study which
11 assessed enjoyment of lunchtime play. As children's cognitive capabilities are developing during
12 elementary school,⁴⁹ the suitability of the survey cards for children aged under 10 years was deemed
13 acceptable based on feedback from elementary school teachers after the initial pilot study.
14 Additionally, face validity of the small survey card was reviewed by five physical activity experts
15 with experience in the development of self-report measures.

16

17 Within the current study enjoyment of lunchtime play survey cards were administered to 197 children
18 aged 8-12 years (112 males, 85 females) from a large government elementary school in regional
19 Victoria, Australia. All grade 3 to 6 children were invited to participate in the study during Winter
20 (June) in school Term 2, 2010 (response rate: 60.8%). Children's 'expected' (before lunch) and
21 'actual' (after lunch) enjoyment of lunchtime play were measured and compared on each day over a
22 five day period (35.9% missing responses). Completion of the survey cards took approximately 20
23 seconds and required children to circle on a five point likert pictorial scale how much they expected to
24 enjoy lunchtime play or how much they actually enjoyed lunchtime play. The enjoyment item was
25 rated on a five-point likert scale from very unhappy (1) to very happy (5). The card also recorded the
26 student name, grade and day of the week. Demographic details such as the child's age and sex were
27 collected from a larger survey as part of the same research project being conducted at the elementary
28 school.

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Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the University Human Research Ethics Committee, the Department of Education and Early Childhood Development in Victoria (DEECD) and permission was gained from the school principal. Children and their parents received a plain language statement outlining the research, along with a participant and parental consent form.

Intra-day and inter-day reliability (including age & sex-specific reliability) of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play were calculated using a Weighted Kappa (k_w^2) statistic for ordinal items.⁵⁰ Kappa values were graded as slight agreement (0.01-0.20), fair agreement (0.21-0.40), moderate agreement (0.41-0.60), substantial agreement (0.61-0.80) and almost perfect agreement (0.81-0.99).⁵⁰ The 95% confidence intervals of weighted kappa were based on the empirical sampling distribution generated by the computer intensive bias corrected bootstrapping re-sampling method.⁵¹ The Z statistic, which follows standard normal distribution with mean 0 and variance 1, was used to compare the level of reliability between sex and age groups.⁵² The values were set at a 5% level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 18 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) was used to calculate the descriptive statistics and R version 2.12.0 (R Development Core Team, Vienna, Austria) was used for the weighted kappa statistics, 95% confidence intervals (CI) and reliability comparisons using Z statistic.

Results

Overall, both 'expected' and 'actual' enjoyment of lunchtime play was rated as very high or high (Table 1). Table 1 presents the intra-day reliability for the enjoyment of lunchtime play between school day one (Wednesday, week one) to school day five (Tuesday, week two). Monday displays substantial kappa agreement, Wednesday and Friday display moderate kappa agreement and Tuesday and Thursday display fair kappa agreement, between expected and actual enjoyment of lunchtime play scores. A decrease in the percentage of enjoyment of lunchtime play was evident from before lunch (expected play enjoyment) to after lunch (actual play enjoyment) across all days. Age and sex-specific intra-day variability in enjoyment of lunchtime play data is also presented (Table 2). Intra-day

1 variability was only significantly different between sexes on Monday (Day 4 of 5), ($Z = 3.66$; $p <$
2 0.001). Monday displayed the highest kappa agreement score for males (almost perfect agreement)
3 and the lowest kappa agreement score for females (fair agreement). Although the intra-day variability
4 was not significantly different on Wednesday, the highest agreement is displayed for females
5 (moderate agreement) and the lowest kappa agreement for males (fair agreement). There were no
6 significant differences in kappa scores between age groups, however the greatest differences in kappa
7 agreement were evident for Tuesday ($Z = 1.71$; $p = 0.09$) and Thursday ($Z = 1.01$; $p = 0.31$). Kappa
8 agreement scores were highest for both age groups on Monday ($Z = 0.24$; $p = 0.81$).

9
10 Inter-day reliability of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play results (Table 2) indicate 'expected'
11 enjoyment of lunchtime play between each of the five days failed to reach moderate kappa agreement,
12 ranging from 0.09 to 0.40 (median kappa=0.30). Similarly low 'actual' inter-day reliability scores for
13 enjoyment of lunchtime play were identified, ranging from 0.05-0.46 (median kappa=0.28). The
14 lowest 'expected' inter-day reliability was between Wednesday and Monday (slight agreement) and
15 the highest 'expected' inter-day reliability was between Monday and Friday (fair agreement). In
16 contrast, the lowest 'actual' inter-day reliability was identified between Tuesday and Wednesday
17 (slight agreement) and the highest 'actual' inter-day reliability was identified between Wednesday and
18 Friday (moderate agreement). No significant differences were identified for age or sex-specific inter-
19 day comparisons (including 79% (63/80) of inter-day comparisons failing to reach moderate
20 reliability), therefore age and sex-specific inter-day lunchtime play enjoyment comparisons are not
21 presented.

22

23 **Discussion**

24 Previous physical activity literature would indicate that the high levels of 'expected' and 'actual'
25 enjoyment of lunchtime play from this study could be correlated with high physical activity
26 participation.^{24, 25} Future research investigating correlations between children's enjoyment of
27 lunchtime play and physical activity participation is therefore warranted. This study identifies the high
28 levels of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play among a sample of elementary school children.

1 Given the concerns regarding the declining levels of physical activity among adolescents^{53, 54} it may
2 be beneficial to examine adolescents' enjoyment of school breaks within a secondary school context.
3 As this is the first study of its kind, we acknowledge that future research should be conducted to
4 further identify patterns of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play; however the large sample size is a
5 strength of the study. In addition, future research is needed to identify the sources and influences of
6 children's enjoyment of lunchtime play. A limitation of the study was the high number of missing
7 responses across the five days, however as the research was conducted within a usual school
8 environment children are absent from school throughout a week for a variety of reasons. It should also
9 be noted that because the research was conducted within a single elementary school, any generalizing
10 of findings are not necessarily representative of the wider population.

11

12 Examination of children's intra-day and inter-day enjoyment of lunchtime play suggests that
13 children's expected and actual enjoyment of lunchtime play is relatively consistent within a single
14 day. However, reliability is lower when comparing children's enjoyment scores of lunchtime play
15 across multiple school days. The higher reliability of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play within a
16 single day may suggest that multiple influences on children's enjoyment within a single school day
17 may cause less variation than across multiple school days. Alternatively it could also mean children
18 can easily remember what their expected enjoyment was when rating their actual enjoyment,
19 potentially biasing the response.

20

21 A theoretical framework that could explain the variation in enjoyment from day to day is the social-
22 ecological model.⁵⁵ The social-ecological model indicates that multiple influences such as
23 intrapersonal (individual), interpersonal (social), physical environment and policy factors within a
24 setting can be modified and affect children's behaviour.⁵⁵ Intrapersonal influences on behaviour
25 includes changes in an individual student's mood; interpersonal influences include variation in family
26 circumstances, behaviour and mood of teachers/peers; physical environment influences include
27 variation in climatic conditions, children's access and availability of play spaces/activities and policy
28 influences may include different/quantity of teachers supervising the playground, changes to rules and

Children's enjoyment of play during school lunchtime breaks

1 access to sports and play equipment or play area allocation by year level. With so many potential
2 influences on children's behaviour from day to day, these factors could be major factors contributing
3 to the low kappa values between days (including 79% of age and sex-specific inter-day kappa
4 comparisons failing to reach moderate reliability).

5

6 The higher reliability for enjoyment of lunchtime play at the beginning of the study (Wednesday,
7 Week 1) and at the beginning of a school week (Monday, Week 2) may reflect that reliability
8 decreases when self-report measures are repeated each day. Children had completed the enjoyment of
9 lunchtime play survey card for the first time on the Wednesday and on the Monday children had
10 experienced the weekend break. In contrast, when the administration of the survey cards were
11 repeated the day after the start of the study and school week, on the Thursday (Week 1) and Tuesday
12 (Week 2), the intra-day reliability dropped from substantial and moderate reliability to a fair level.
13 Although intra-day reliability for Friday (Week 1) was moderate, the findings suggest that reliability
14 may be increased if administration of the self-report is spaced out over time, rather than repeating
15 each day.

16

17 It should be acknowledged that the lower intra-day reliability (fair) of lunchtime enjoyment scores on
18 the final day (Tuesday) could be attributed to five days being too many days of repeated measures.
19 Thursday (Day 2) could also have been affected by the cooler weather (maximum temperature
20 $<10^{\circ}\text{C}$), as the mean maximum temperature for the other four days was 11.7°C ($\text{sd}=0.76$).
21 Temperature variation has been found to influence children's physical activity^{12, 56} and this could also
22 be the case for correlates of physical activity such as enjoyment of play. In addition, it should also be
23 noted that lower percentages of 'actual' enjoyment of play after lunch may suggest children could be
24 more optimistic about enjoying lunchtime play before lunchtime commences. This would be due to
25 children being unable to predict or take into account potential influences on their play that can occur
26 during lunchtime breaks that may affect their level of enjoyment.

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Children's enjoyment of play during school lunchtime breaks

1 The greatest intra-day kappa score differences between males and females earlier in the week could
2 indicate that administering self-report measures earlier in the school week may detect greater sex
3 differences than later in the school week. This is reinforced by a significant kappa score difference
4 between males and females for Monday (day four). Before children experience the demands of
5 different subjects, homework and other school commitments of the school week, children could be
6 taking more time and be more specific when rating the enjoyment of lunchtime play survey, resulting
7 in the sex differences in kappa scores being more identifiable. Another possibility could be due to
8 Monday (day four) and Tuesday (day five) being the final two days of the study and having completed
9 repeated measures over the previous three days may have resulted in one of the sex's being less
10 accurate in self-reporting their enjoyment of lunchtime play during the fourth and fifth days of survey
11 administration. In other words, the boys quite simply may have been 'over it!' Evidence also suggests
12 males and females participate in and prefer different physical activities⁵⁷ and behaviour⁵⁸ during
13 school lunchtime play, which could have influenced sex-specific differences in kappa agreement.
14 Interestingly, female enjoyment scores were most reliable and males were least reliable during the
15 start of the study (Wednesday/Day one) between 'expected' and 'actual' enjoyment of lunchtime play.
16 In contrast, male enjoyment of lunchtime play scores contained 'almost perfect' reliability at the start
17 of the school week (Monday/Day four), the day in which females possessed their lowest reliability
18 (fair agreement) between 'expected' and 'actual' enjoyment of lunchtime play.

19

20 An important finding from the study was the similar kappa agreement scores between the 8-9 and 10-
21 12 year old age groups. Although previous research that has examined enjoyment of sport and
22 physical activity suggests that children's sources of enjoyment varies with age,²³ reliability
23 comparisons between the age groups were relatively consistent. Similar to the males, both age groups
24 possessed enjoyment of lunchtime play scores that displayed very high reliability on Monday
25 (substantial agreement) and the high intra-day reliability for both age groups on Monday may suggest
26 that administering self-report enjoyment measures on a Monday could strongly represent enjoyment
27 of play throughout that school day.

28

1 This is the first study we are aware of to examine the intra-day and inter-day reliability of enjoyment
2 of lunchtime play. There is a lack of consensus as to how many days of measurement are required to
3 assess children's enjoyment of lunchtime, therefore a typical school week (five days) was chosen. The
4 moderate intra-day reliability of enjoyment of lunchtime play for three out of five school days
5 suggests that assessing children's enjoyment of play after lunch would be representative of enjoyment
6 of lunchtime play on that particular day, but not necessarily that school week. It should be
7 acknowledged this study relied on children under 12 years of age accurately predicting and recalling
8 enjoyment play during school lunchtime. Concerns have previously been raised about using self-
9 report instruments with elementary aged children,⁴⁹ however we minimized this potential
10 complication by piloting the survey cards and by considering the format of the questionnaire and
11 employing the use of a pictorial scale using developmentally appropriate images of smiley faces.⁵⁹

12

13 **Conclusion**

14 In summary, this research addresses a significant gap in the literature by examining the reliability of
15 children's enjoyment of lunchtime play across multiple days. The level of reliability between
16 children's 'expected' and 'actual' enjoyment of lunchtime play scores reached at least moderate
17 agreement for most days. This acceptable agreement within most of the school days suggests that
18 measuring children's 'expected' or 'actual' enjoyment of lunchtime play is likely to represent that
19 particular school day. In contrast, only a very small proportion of inter-day comparisons for
20 enjoyment of lunch time play reached a moderate level of reliability. This may indicate that factors
21 influencing children's experiences from day to day may affect the variation of enjoyment scores on
22 other school days and therefore may not necessarily be representative of children's enjoyment of
23 lunchtime play across different days of the week. Generally, children expected to enjoy lunchtime
24 play in greater proportions than they actually did, indicating children expect to have a positive
25 experience during their school lunchtime play. The findings suggest that age didn't appear to affect
26 the reliability of enjoyment scores in the sample surveyed, however sex can be an influential factor on
27 the overall reliability of a group's enjoyment of lunchtime play.

28

1 **Practical implications**

- 2 • The reliability of children's enjoyment of lunchtime play within a single day suggests that
3 measurement once on a single day would be representative of that particular day but not
4 necessarily that school week.
- 5 • The findings suggest that future physical activity interventions targeting school lunch periods
6 should consider spacing out the assessment of enjoyment across multiple days.

7

8 **Acknowledgements**

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12 research was conducted at XXXX University. We would also like to acknowledge Professor
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Table 1: Intra-day reliability including age and sex-specific intra-day variability (weighted kappa (95% CI)) of children’s enjoyment of school lunchtime play.

	‘Expected’ Enjoyment of Lunchtime Play			‘Actual’ Enjoyment of Lunchtime Play			Intra-day variability (weighted kappa (95%CI))								
							Sex				Age				Intra-day Reliability
Day	VH/H %	NS %	VU/U %	VH/H %	NS %	VU/U %	Male (Weighted Kappa (95% CI))	Female (Weighted Kappa (95% CI))	Z	P Value [†]	8-9 Years (Weighted Kappa (95% CI))	10-12 Years (Weighted Kappa (95% CI))	Z	P Value [†]	Overall
Wednesday (1)	94.7	4.3	1.0	88.1	6.7	5.2	0.27 (-0.05–0.59)	0.55 (0.19 – 0.91)	1.17	0.24	0.54 (0.14 – 0.94)	0.40 (0.08 – 0.73)	0.51	0.61	0.49 (0.15-0.76)
Thursday (2)	93.0	5.4	1.6	91.7	4.8	3.5	0.29 (0.07 – 0.52)	0.34 (0.01 – 0.67)	0.22	0.83	0.40 (0.18 – 0.63)	0.22 (-0.04 – 0.49)	1.01	0.31	0.31 (0.11-0.50)
Friday (3)	89.9	7.2	2.9	84.7	6.5	8.8	0.42 (0.09 – 0.76)	0.37 (0.02 – 0.72)	0.21	0.84	0.45 (0.10 – 0.80)	0.33 (-0.02 – 0.67)	0.48	0.63	0.41 (0.17-0.66)
Monday (4)	93.9	3.0	3.1	89.8	6.1	4.1	0.87 (0.76 – 0.98)	0.32 (0.05 – 0.60)	3.66	<0.001*	0.71 (0.49 – 0.93)	0.77 (0.40 – 0.98)	0.24	0.81	0.75 (0.50-0.90)
Tuesday (5)	95.5	3.6	0.9	86.2	7.6	6.2	0.28 (0.08 – 0.48)	0.36 (0.26 – 0.46)	0.72	0.47	0.24 (0.07 – 0.40)	0.42 (0.29 – 0.56)	1.71	0.09	0.32 (0.21-0.44)

CI= confidence interval; Day 1-5 represents the order of testing with the first day of testing beginning on a Wednesday

Z= Standard Normal variate; † P value from the standard normal test (Z test); CI= confidence interval; *= Significant difference

VH/H= Very Happy/Happy; NS= Not Sure; VU/U= Very Unhappy/Unhappy

Table 2: Inter-day reliability of children’s enjoyment of school lunchtime play. The upper panel shows the ‘expected’ and the lower panel shows the ‘actual’ enjoyment of lunchtime play.

Weighted Kappa (95% CI)				
Wednesday (1)	-	-	-	-
0.35 (0.10 - 0.57)				
0.25 (0.06 - 0.43)	Thursday (2)	-	-	-
0.10 (-0.09 - 0.36)	0.37 (0.15 - 0.57)	Friday (3)	-	-
0.46 (0.20 - 0.70)	0.19 (-0.02 - 0.49)			
0.09 (-0.10 - 0.30)	0.33 (0.08 - 0.55)	0.40 (0.17 - 0.62)	Monday (4)	-
0.14 (-0.08 - 0.41)	0.09 (-0.06 - 0.30)	0.44 (0.10 - 0.72)		
0.16 (0.01 - 0.31)	0.28 (0.19 - 0.39)	0.27 (0.14 - 0.44)	0.31 (0.19 - 0.56)	Tuesday (5)
0.05 (-0.10 - 0.28)	0.30 (0.07 - 0.53)	0.37 (0.11 - 0.65)	0.41 (0.09 - 0.71)	

CI= confidence interval; Day 1-5 represents the order of testing with the first day of testing beginning on a Wednesday